

ACHIEVEMENTS AND DISADVANTAGES OF THE INDUSTRY OF ANDIJAN REGION IN THE PERIOD OF 1946-1991

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Abstract: *This article provides brief information about the achievements and shortcomings of Andijan region's industry in the period 1946-1991, the surface of Andijan region, relief and rocks on the surface, the current industry of Andijan, and minerals.*

Key words: *Terrain, geological, shareholding, plows, metropolis, industry.*

The land surface of Andijan region is mostly flat. The current relief and rocks on the earth's surface were formed by the activity of large and small rivers and tributaries of the Quaternary geological period. The western part of the region consists of a mountainous plain (400-500 m above sea level), and the eastern part (on the outskirts of Andijan city) consists of branches of the Fergana and Olay ridges.

As for the current industry of Andijan, 48 large modern industrial enterprises, 63 construction organizations and local industrial enterprises are working in the city. Joint-stock companies such as "Andijonmash", "Andijonirmash" produce equipment for cotton factories, parts for agricultural machines, pumps, universal loaders, rotary plows, wheelchairs for the disabled and other equipment. Diesel pumps and pumps, universal loaders produced in Andijan are exported to other countries. Andijan enterprises produce electronics ("Elektrodivigatel", "Elektroapparat" joint-stock companies) and machines. "Biokimyo" plant produces ethyl alcohol, etheraldehyde fraction, carbonic acid and animal feed (see Andijan Biochemical Plant). There are sewing and shoe factories. Local industrial enterprises also specialize in the production of shoes, decorative tapestry, furniture and household goods. All branches of the food industry are developed in Andijan. There are 50 joint ventures in the city (USA, China, Great Britain, Republic of Korea, in cooperation with Russia, Italy, Kyrgyzstan and others). 5 of them produce auto parts for the joint venture "UzDEUavto". Year after year, new joint ventures are launched in the city, and the production of modern and export-oriented products is launched. There are

about 3,000 small and medium-sized business entities and more than 7,000 private entrepreneurs in the city.

We will pay attention to how the Andijan industry was in 1946-1991. Mining of mineral resources and cotton growing in the province were used as raw materials and sent to the metropolis. In 1907, a semi-artisanal oil factory was built. Initially, this plant processed 50 tons of seeds and produced about 8 tons of oil in one night. In 1954, the factory was transformed into an oil-oil combine. In 1960-70, large enterprises such as "Elektrodivigatel", "Elektroapparat" and "Elektrotehnika" plant were built in Andijan. In 1941, a motor factory was launched in the city of Andijan. During the years of independence, the industry of the region changed its direction and developed radically. Existing enterprises are being taken out of state ownership and entering a special form of ownership. In particular, joint-stock companies were established on the basis of most large and medium-sized enterprises. There are 160 industrial enterprises of all types of ownership in the region (2000). The largest of them are: Bobur yarn production joint-stock company (in Andijan city; there are branches in the districts), "Andijan Agrofirma" joint-stock company, Andijan car seat factory, Andijan biochemical plant, Andijan irrigation machinery plant, Andijan "Semurg" knitwear joint-stock association, Andijan grain products" joint-stock company, "Andijonkabel joint-stock company", Chinabad cotton-ginning joint-stock company. During 1991-2000, modern joint enterprises producing world-class products were created in Andijan region. There are 79 joint enterprises, 8447 small and private enterprises in the region. Joint enterprises in the region produce more than 53% of the gross industrial product of the entire region (2000). The only automobile manufacturing enterprise in Central Asia is the Uzbek-South Korean "UzDEU auto" company located in Asaka. Italy's "Federichi Brothers" The Uzbek-Italian joint venture "FAM" established in Asaka in cooperation with the joint-stock company has the production capacity of 1-1.5 tons of pasta per hour, depending on the type. In the village of Segazaqum in the Shahrikhan district, the open joint-stock company "ANTEKS" was established, which produces kalava yarn and in the future will weave gauze from it. - gas industry, hosiery factories, etc.), the food industry is the most developed industry. The region occupies an important place in the production of oil and gas in the country. About ten oil and oil-gas fields (Andijan oil field, "Khojaabad", "Boston", "Janubiy Olamushuk", "Khartum", "Polvontosh", "Khojausman" and others) are working. There is a Khojaabad-Andijan-Asaka gas pipeline. The first cotton ginning factories in Andijan region were built in Andijan in 1911, in Asaka in

1912, and in Shahrikhan in 1915. This type of industry developed rapidly based on cotton cultivation. In 1924, 25 thousand tons of raw materials were processed in cotton factories. In 1999, more than 325 thousand tons of cotton were processed in 13 existing cotton processing enterprises. The cocoons, wool, and skins grown in the region were not processed at all and were put into operation in October 1999). The Uzbek-American joint venture in the form of a closed joint-stock company for the production of non-woven fabrics of Balıkhchi District is one of the enterprises that has gained attention abroad with its products. The joint venture was re-equipped with modern equipment. More than 1,300 workers work in this enterprise, which produces kalava yarn and raw gas (2000). Andijan-Praga, Andijan Durdonasi, Navigul, Uz-Koromko, Uzbek-Russian-British "Mask", "Al-Asia" joint enterprises and Uzbek-American joint ventures have attracted investments from developed countries in the region. The company has a branch.

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